

Additional document for “Co-optimization of GFM Converter Proportion and Control Parameters for Renewable Power Plants in Weak Grids”

APPENDIXES OF THE MANUSCRIPT

A. Modeling of Hybrid Grid-Following/Grid-Forming Converter Systems:

Following the modeling approach in Fig. 1, the mathematical models of grid-following converters, grid-forming converters, and the AC network are combined through coordinate transformation and linearized at the equilibrium point, yielding the integrated station-level state-space model in (1), (2),(3),(4).

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of coordinate transformation and subsystem interaction relationships

$$\Delta u_{DQ} = R_N \left(n_{GFL} \Delta i_{oDQGFL} + n_{GFM} \Delta i_{oDQGFM} + \Delta i_{DQgrid} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\Delta x} = \mathbf{A} \Delta x \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{GFL} + R_N n_{GFL} B_{GFL} C_{GFL} & R_N n_{GFM} B_{GFL} C_{GFM} & R_N B_{GFL} C_{GRID} \\ R_N n_{GFL} B_{GFM} C_{GFL} & A_{GFM} + R_N n_{GFM} B_{GFM} C_{GFM} & R_N B_{GFM} C_{GRID} \\ R_N n_{GFL} B_{GRID} C_{GFL} & R_N n_{GFM} B_{GRID} C_{GFM} & A_{GRID} + R_N B_{GRID} C_{GRID} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta x = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \varphi_{pll} & \Delta \delta_{GFL} & \Delta \psi_{GFL,PQ} & \Delta \gamma_{GFL,dq} & \Delta i_{GFL,odq} & \Delta \omega_{GFM} \\ \Delta \delta_{GFM} & \Delta E_{GFM} & \Delta \varphi_{GFM,dq} & \Delta \gamma_{GFM,dq} & \Delta i_{GFM,odq} & \Delta i_{gdq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where: n_{GFL} represents the proportion of GFL converters, and n_{GFM} denotes the proportion of GFM converters. Δx contains the state variables of the GFL, GFM, and grid modules, which are sequentially organized as follows: the q-axis voltage integral term, phase-locked loop angle, power outer-loop integral term, current inner-loop integral term, and output current of the GFL; the frequency, phase angle, internal electromotive force, voltage outer-loop integral term, current inner-loop integral term, and output current of the GFM; and the grid line current. Through the coupling point formula given in Equation (4), these variables form the complete state-space equations. Matrix \mathbf{A} is the system state matrix, and small-signal stability relates to the eigenvalues of this matrix.

B. Analytical Expression for Small-Signal Stability Sensitivity:

To quantify system dynamic behavior, according to Lyapunov's second method, the eigenvalue optimization problem for matrices is often formulated as a linear semidefinite programming problem shown in Equation (5).

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \zeta \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & -\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P} - \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A} + 2\zeta \mathbf{I} \succ 0 \\ & \mathbf{P} \succ 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where \mathbf{P} is a real symmetric positive definite matrix, and ζ is a real variable whose value after solving the model equals the spectral abscissa of matrix \mathbf{A} .

The Lyapunov function-based method provides a holistic assessment of stability, encompassing both system stability and convergence rate. This paper adopts stability index ζ derived from the Lyapunov function due to its superior practical utility. Unlike eigenvalue analysis, stability index ζ is formulated as a convex semidefinite programming problem possessing strong duality. Leveraging this strong duality, we compute stability sensitivity with analytical precision while significantly reducing computational burden. This approach is applicable for stability assessment and convergence rate evaluation, while oscillation mode analysis is excluded from consideration.

The stability constraint can be expressed as: $\zeta(k) < \bar{\zeta}$, where k represents the controllable variables available for enhancing the stability index, $\bar{\zeta}$ represents the stability index limit. To ensure the stability index satisfies the constraint, it is necessary to adjust k by computing the corresponding sensitivity. However, since the functional relationship between ζ and k is implicit, determining this sensitivity is highly challenging. The mainstream sensitivity analysis method is numerical perturbation, and the estimation method for the stability sensitivity with respect to k is given in (6).

$$\left. \frac{d\zeta}{dk} \right|_{k=k^0} \approx \frac{\zeta(k^0 + \varepsilon) - \zeta(k^0)}{\varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

However, this estimation result is highly dependent on the perturbation value ε , rendering the numerical perturbation method inaccurate. Moreover, since calculating the stability index twice is required to obtain the sensitivity for a single variable k , the computational burden is significant. This paper proposes an analytical formula for precisely computing stability sensitivity. Leveraging the convexity of

semidefinite programming, we derive the analytical expression for the Jacobian matrix element sensitivity

$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial A_{ij}}$, and then obtain the stability sensitivity $\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial k}$ using the chain rule of differentiation.

The original form of the aforementioned semidefinite programming problem is reformulated into its standard form as shown in (7).

$$\begin{aligned} & \min \mathbf{c}^T \boldsymbol{\phi} \\ & \text{s.t. } \mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\phi}, A_{ij}) \succeq \mathbf{0} \\ & \mathbf{F}_i(A_{ij}) \in \mathbb{S}^{3n}, i = 0, 1, \dots, m \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where: $\mathbf{c} = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^T$, Vector $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ includes the stability index η and the lower triangular elements $\Phi_{11}, \Phi_{21}, \Phi_{22}, \Phi_{31}, \Phi_{32}, \Phi_{33}, \dots, \Phi_m$ of the symmetric matrix $\boldsymbol{\Phi}$, $\mathbf{c}, \boldsymbol{\phi} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $m = 1 + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$. Considering all constraints in the original semidefinite programming problem, we define $\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\phi}, A_{ij}) = \mathbf{F}_0 + \mathbf{F}_1 \phi_1 + \dots + \mathbf{F}_m \phi_m$, where $\mathbf{F}_i = \text{diag}\{\mathbf{F}_i^{(1)}, \mathbf{F}_i^{(2)}, \mathbf{F}_i^{(3)}\}$, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(1)}, \mathbf{F}_i^{(2)}, \mathbf{F}_i^{(3)} \in \mathbb{S}^n$, \mathbb{S}^n denotes the set of all n-dimensional real symmetric matrices. Corresponding to the constraints in the aforementioned original semidefinite programming problem: $\mathbf{F}_0^{(1)} = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{F}_1^{(1)} = \mathbf{I}$, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(1)} = -\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{T}_i - \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{F}_0^{(2)} = -\epsilon \mathbf{I}$, $\mathbf{F}_1^{(2)} = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(2)} = \mathbf{T}_i$, $\mathbf{F}_0^{(3)} = \mathbf{I}$, $\mathbf{F}_1^{(3)} = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{F}_i^{(3)} = -\mathbf{T}_i$, $\{\mathbf{T}_i\}$ represents the basis for n-dimensional symmetric matrices, $i = 2, \dots, m$.

The standard form of the dual problem for this semidefinite programming is given in (8).

$$\begin{aligned} & \max -\text{Tr} \mathbf{F}_0 \mathbf{Z} \\ & \text{s.t. } \text{Tr} \mathbf{F}_i(A_{ij}) \mathbf{Z} = c_i \\ & \mathbf{Z} \succeq \mathbf{0} \\ & \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{S}^{3n}, i = 1, \dots, m \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the symmetric matrix \mathbf{Z} represents the dual variable corresponding to the primal variable $\boldsymbol{\phi}$.

For notational and computational convenience, we define the function "svec" that maps \mathbb{S}^n to \mathbb{R}^{m-1} , $\mathbf{z} = \text{svec}(\mathbf{Z}) \triangleq [Z_{11}, \sqrt{2}Z_{12}, \dots, \sqrt{2}Z_{1n}, Z_{22}, \sqrt{2}Z_{23}, \dots, Z_{nn}]^T$. Additionally, the symmetric Kronecker

product \otimes is employed to simplify expressions, defined such that for any n-dimensional symmetric matrix \mathbf{X} , there exist $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ making (9) hold.

$$(\mathbf{M} \otimes \mathbf{N})\text{svec}(\mathbf{X}) \triangleq \text{svec}\left(\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{N}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{M}^T + \mathbf{M}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{N}^T)\right) \quad (9)$$

Through the derivation process, the sensitivity of the Jacobian matrix elements can be obtained as shown in (10)-(15).

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{k}}{\partial A_{ij}} \Big|_{A_{ij}=A_{ij}^0} = -\mathbf{G}'(\mathbf{k}^*, A_{ij}^0)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial A_{ij}} \Big|_{\mathbf{k}^*, A_{ij}^0} \quad (10)$$

Where:

$$\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{k}, A_{ij}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}(A_{ij})^T \mathbf{z} - \mathbf{c} \\ (\mathbf{Z} \otimes \mathbf{I})\text{svec}(\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\phi}, A_{ij})) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{G}'(\mathbf{k}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathcal{F}(A_{ij})^T \\ (\mathbf{Z} \otimes \mathbf{I})\mathcal{F}(A_{ij}) & \mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\phi}, A_{ij}) \otimes \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial A_{ij}} = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial A_{ij}}\right)^T \mathbf{z} \\ (\mathbf{Z} \otimes \mathbf{I})\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial A_{ij}} \boldsymbol{\phi} + \text{sec}\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_0}{\partial A_{ij}}\right)\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = [\boldsymbol{\phi}^T, \mathbf{z}^T]^T \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{F}(A_{ij}) \triangleq \left[\text{svec}(\mathbf{F}_1(A_{ij})), \dots, \text{svec}(\mathbf{F}_m(A_{ij})) \right] \quad (15)$$

It should be noted that the first element of vector $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ is the stability index ζ . For concise representation, vector \mathbf{k} is defined to include $\boldsymbol{\phi}$, hence the stability index ζ is also the first element of \mathbf{k} .

Finally, by applying the chain rule of differentiation, the sensitivity of the stability index ζ with respect to the controllable variable \mathbf{k} is obtained as shown in (16).

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mathbf{k}} = \sum_{i,j} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial A_{ij}} \cdot \frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial \mathbf{k}} \quad (16)$$

Here, $\frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial k}$ represents the partial derivative of the Jacobian matrix elements (which contain k)

with respect to k . Since each Jacobian matrix element is an explicit function of k , this partial derivative can be derived efficiently.

C. Main Parameters of the New Energy Plant, Grid-Forming and Grid-Following Converters:

	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Value</i>
Plant and line parameters	Converter rated capacity	10MW
	Converter quantity	50 sets
	Transformer transformation ratio	0.69kV/ 110kV
	Line impedance, impedance ratio	0.02, 0.5
GFM control parameters	Virtual inertia time coefficient T_J	1
	Damping coefficient D	50
	Reactive power droop coefficient k_Q	0.5
	Voltage outer loop PI parameters k_{pv} , k_{iv}	5, 50
	Current inner loop PI parameters k_{pc} , k_{ic}	0.5, 50
GFL control parameters	Phase-locked loop PI parameters k_{ppll} , k_{ipll}	10, 1000
	Power outer loop PI parameters k_{pp} , k_{ip}	1, 60
	Current inner loop PI parameters k_{pc} , k_{ic}	0.5,50